

Confucian Culture and Corporate True Surplus Management: Facilitation or Inhibition?—Based on the Perspective of Internal and External Monitoring Mechanisms of Listed Companies

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Abstract

As the requirements for quality of accounting information continue to be rigorous, corporate surplus management is gradually biased toward using real business for it. Real surplus management behavior is covert and private, and can damage the long-term value of enterprises, so how to curb real surplus management behavior is an important issue worth studying. This paper selects a sample of listed companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen A-shares from 2015- 2019 to test the influence of Confucianism. This paper selects a sample of listed companies in Shanghai and Shenzhen A-shares from 2015-2019 to test the influence of Confucian culture on corporate true surplus management from an informal institutional perspective. It is found that the two are significantly negatively correlated, and this relationship is more prominent among non-state enterprises, growth stage enterprises and Further research finds that Confucian culture can complement the internal and external Further research finds that Confucian culture can complement the internal and external monitoring mechanisms of firms, with external audits reinforcing this disincentive effect and internal controls reinforcing the moderating effect in The Confucian culture can complement the internal and external monitoring mechanisms of firms, with external audits reinforcing this disincentive effect and internal controls reinforcing the moderating effect in firms with more effective internal controls.

Key words: Real earnings management, informal system, Confucian culture, internal monitoring, external monitoring

I. Introduction

Confucianism is the most important representative of China's informal system, which is very rich in economic thinking. Confucianism, as a unique cultural institution, implicitly influences the economic behaviour of various market players and has received the attention of scholars in many fields in recent years. A growing number of scholars believe that Confucian traditions commonly permeate the values of modern Chinese businessmen, thus influencing their business decisions and governance behaviour. ^[1] Studying the influence of Confucian culture on business activities based on this implicit perspective can help to understand the value of China's traditional culture in economic behaviour.

Surplus management has long been a hot topic of research for domestic and international scholars. In addition to the manipulation of unusual accruals, academics have found that management can use more covert real trading activities to carry out surplus management, thereby misleading stakeholders. Its characteristics of high concealment, low litigation risk and high accounting flexibility make it the most important way of surplus management for listed enterprises in China ^[2], thus demonstrating the importance of systematic research on real surplus management.

Therefore, the article attempts to explore the effect of informal institutions on corporate decision-making behaviour based on Confucian culture in relation to true surplus management, and introduces internal monitoring mechanisms and external monitoring mechanisms as moderating variables to explore the mechanisms of their moderating effects.

II. Literature Review

(i) Studies on Confucianism

1. Confucian cultural and institutional background

Confucianism is an important part of traditional Chinese culture. Confucius started his own system of thought in the Spring and Autumn period, and it gradually formed a complete system of thought through the vigorous promotion and development of Mencius and Xunzi. ³[During the Qin Dynasty, Confucianism was severely undermined by the Qin Emperor, who regarded Confucianism as an enemy and ordered the burning of books and the burying of Confucianism. In the Han dynasty, Emperor Wu of Han Dynasty advocated "dismissing the hundred schools of thought and respecting only Confucianism", and since then Confucianism has been revered by the court and has become the official school and state religion, occupying an important place in Chinese history and culture. From the "contention of the hundred schools of thought" in the pre-Qin dynasty to the "exclusive respect for Confucianism" in the Han dynasty, Confucianism gradually developed into the mainstream of Chinese thought. ⁴]

For a long time, Confucianism has been the moral code of the people in Chinese society that they "use every day without being aware of it". ⁵[Although Confucianism has suffered to some extent from globalisation and the invasion of Western cultures, its influence on the overall tone of popular thought is still widely recognised.

2. The influence of Confucian culture on corporate decision-making

Confucian culture is rich in connotations and has a profound influence on politics, society and the economy. A number of scholars have now empirically explored the significant guiding role of Confucian culture on business operations, focusing on corporate innovation, corporate social responsibility, corporate governance and risk-taking capabilities.

(1) Confucian culture and corporate innovation

Confucianism embodies the spirit of self-improvement and pioneering, such as "Although the Zhou is an old state, its fate is new"; it also emphasises respect for knowledge and the importance of talent, such as: "to promote virtuous talents" and "to be courteous to the virtuous". "Both of these will promote innovation in enterprises. The results of Xu Xiexiong and Li Wanli et al. (2019) ⁶] show that the degree of Confucianism has a significant incentive effect on the level of innovation in enterprises. A wider range of empirical evidence was conducted by Bo Cheng et al. (2018) ⁷], and the findings showed that Confucianism has a positive effect on employees' on-the-job training and a company's ability to innovate.

(2) Confucianism and Corporate Social Responsibility

The "benevolent government" is one of the representative ideas of Confucianism, which is embodied in "the benevolent person loves people", "love all people in general" and "kiss the people and be kind to them". "To a certain extent, it can encourage the company to take up social responsibility. Internally, it is manifested in the care for employees. Kam Weiyu et al. (2020) ⁸] found that Confucian culture significantly influenced corporate employment strategies and improved the quality of employee rights and interests protection. Externally manifested in responsibility to the public, Huang Guoliang (2019) ⁹] found through empirical research that the more deeply influenced by Confucian culture, the higher the level of social responsibility undertaken by enterprises, and this phenomenon is more obvious in regions with a higher degree of marketization. Xu Hsiu-hsiung et al. (2020) ¹⁰] took A-share listed companies from 2007-2016 as a data sample and obtained the conclusion that the degree of Confucian cultural influence was positively related to the probability and expenditure of corporate charitable giving behaviour.

(3) Confucianism and Corporate Governance

The core concepts of Confucius are "benevolence, righteousness, propriety, wisdom and trust", and "sincerity as the basis and trust as the foundation" is the basic character of Confucianism, which is the cornerstone of a company's existence and its second life. Cheng Bo and Xiong Ting et al. (2018) ^[11]] take family businesses of Chinese listed companies as an example, and through empirical analysis, find that Confucian culture can effectively reduce the illegal phenomenon of Chinese listed companies. Hu Shaohua et al. (2021) ^[12]] expanded the study sample to include enterprises in Shanghai and Shenzhen, and the empirical results showed that Confucianism could significantly inhibit the types of violations such as operation and information disclosure of enterprises.

(4) Confucianism and corporate risk-taking

Jinz et al. (2017) ^[13]] selected 13 years of data from domestic listed companies and empirically found a significant negative correlation between the degree of corporate influence by Confucianism and the degree of risk-taking, indicating that corporate management prefers risk avoidance under the influence of Confucian traditions. Khaliletal.(2019) ^[14]], on the other hand, studied the relationship between Confucian culture and the risk of stock price collapse and found a significant negative correlation. Domestic scholars Xu Hsiu-hsiung et al. (2020) ^[15]] reached similar conclusions, and the empirical results suggest that Confucian culture would reduce the risk of a firm's stock market crash through three paths: inhibiting executive self-interest, improving the quality of corporate information and reducing management overconfidence.

(ii) Research on true corporate surplus management

1. The meaning and existence of true surplus management

Surplus management has long been a hot topic of international research, referring to the way in which corporate management adjusts accounting earnings information to maximise its own interests while complying with accounting standards. In 1989, Schipper classified two types of surplus management, one is accrual surplus management which uses accounting judgment to manipulate book surplus, and the other is real surplus management which deliberately constructs real trading activities or changes the timing of transactions to manipulate profits. ^[16]] Roychowdhury in 2006 provided a more academic definition of true surplus management: "economic activity that is deliberately created by managers to mislead investors and deviate from the normal operating activities of the business", which is the more accepted definition in academic circles. ^[17]]

The existence of true surplus management has also been studied by domestic and international scholars. The results show that in accounting practice, there is a great deal of real surplus management in addition to the treatment of accrual surpluses. Firstly, Roychowdhury (2006) provides a comprehensive analysis of the existence of real surplus management in micro-profit companies and finds evidence that firms use real business manipulation to manage their surpluses to avoid losses. . There have been many overseas studies on the existence of real surplus management, which have largely established the existence of the use of real surplus management techniques in companies to manipulate profits.

Relatively speaking, most of the relevant domestic literature focuses on accrual surplus management, and little research has been conducted on the existence of true surplus management behaviours, but this does not mean that true surplus management behaviours do not exist among domestic enterprises. Li Zengfu et al. (2011) ^[18]] analysed the surplus management behaviour of listed companies in China in equity refinancing and the impact on company performance, and the results showed that listed companies would use both accrual and true surplus management to carry out accounting manipulation.

2. Instruments of true surplus management

The above literature proves that true surplus management does exist in the surplus management activities of companies. Through analysis of the extensive literature, I believe that the five main areas of true surplus

management tools of companies revolve around sales control, expense control, production control, asset sales and stock repurchases. ^[19]

(1) Sales control

Sales control is mainly through sales discounts and relaxation of credit terms to increase sales and avoid losses. Jackson (2000) ^[20] found in a survey of marginally profitable companies that company management would choose to pursue sales discount strategies at the end of the year to improve performance and ensure eventual profit growth, and Roychowdhury (2006) found the same conclusion in his study.

(2) Cost control

In order to meet revenue targets, senior management may choose to reduce current expenses at their discretion in order to manipulate corporate profits, which has been found to be a relatively common phenomenon by foreign scholars. Graham, Harvey & Rajgopal (2005) ^[21], Gunny (2010) ^[22] and others have found that when the ability to manipulate accounting is limited, listed companies usually resort to cutting discretionary expenses such as reducing research funding to increase short-term surpluses, reducing operating and management costs, and reducing capital investment. However, such surplus management techniques, by reducing expensed expenditure on research and development and marketing activities, while superficially increasing company profits in the short term, undermine long-term growth capacity and come at the expense of company value.

(3) Production control

When firms are unable to increase profits by expanding sales, they can also reduce the cost per unit of product by employing overproduction to achieve desired economic goals. Zhang (2002) ^[23] found that cost reduction behaviour using overproduction exists in firms. Gupta et al. (2010) found that in overproduction years, firms with high fixed production costs had ROA is also higher; while in later years, the ROA of firms that are most likely to have engaged in surplus management will decline. ^[24] In the long run, an increase in production leads to an increase in inventories, tying up large amounts of capital and reducing the efficiency of capital use, thus increasing the value of inventories and losses. In this way, production control is actually detrimental to the value of the company.

(4) Sale of assets

Companies can sell assets to obtain cash or other marketable securities, so when the company's performance is not up to standard, they can sell assets to obtain proceeds to bring profits up to the expected level. Bala G. Dharan and Baruch Lev (1993) ^[25] study shows that 73% of companies have tried to replace accounting treatment by disposal of assets in times of financial difficulties in order to prevent the reported earnings deterioration. In addition, Herrmann et al. (2003) ^[26] conducted a survey of Japanese listed companies and showed that managers may also choose to engage in true surplus management through the sale of movable assets. Li Qin et al. (2007) ^[27] pointed out that listed companies in China also sell assets to increase company earnings in order to meet the requirements of share placement or additional issue, in addition, if the transfer of control of the enterprise occurs, it will also dispose of assets to achieve a turnaround or prevent a decline in performance.

(5) Share buybacks

Earnings per share is an important predictor of performance for economic analysts, and Hribar et al. (2006) ^[28] find that when firms fail to meet economic forecasts, they typically buy back a large and unusual number of shares before each quarter, and that marginally loss-making firms are relatively more likely to engage in share buybacks. Bens (2002) ^[29] find that when corporate executives use share buybacks for true surplus management can mitigate the dilutive effect of executing employee option plans on EPS.

3. Economic consequences of true surplus management

Real surplus management is closer to profit manipulation in practice and is more secretive. Scholars are currently examining and testing the economic consequences of real surplus management primarily on the

basis of real surplus management techniques, and there are currently two contrasting academic views on the economic consequences.

One view is that true surplus management can have serious adverse economic consequences for the firm. Firstly, through production, sales and expense manipulation, it can help companies achieve their performance forecast targets in the short term, but it can also affect the normal operation of the company, thus affecting its long-term development. Cohen et al (2010) ^[30]] find empirically that true surplus management practices are negatively associated with performance in subsequent years. In China, similar conclusions have been reached by scholars. Li Zengfu et al (2012) ^[31]], through an empirical analysis of listed companies in China, found that there is a certain amount of financial risk in true surplus management, leading to long-term performance decline.

Another view is that true surplus management can improve the future performance of a company or convey a good outlook to the market. In contrast to the findings of most scholars, Taylor & Xu (2010) ^[32]] empirically show that true surplus management does not have a significant negative impact on future business performance, and the findings suggest that true surplus management is a contingent behaviour with a limited degree of impact on firms. Gunny (2010) argues, based on signalling theory, that achieving performance forecasts through true surplus management that it can create a good image in the minds of stakeholders such as creditors, suppliers and customers. In a further study, it was found that true surplus management would have a positive impact on a company's operating performance in later years. Graham et al (2005) ^[33]] found that: 86.3% of corporate executives believed that achieving surplus standards could improve confidence in the capital market, which could help investors understand the company's growth prospects. ^[134]

The above literature suggests that there is not yet a general academic consensus on the economic consequences of true surplus management, but most academics are biased towards agreeing that true surplus management damages the long-term value of companies and also affects the role of capital markets in resource allocation.

(iii) Literature Review

Overall, research in the area of both Confucian culture and true surplus management has been gradually gaining attention from both domestic and international scholars, but there is still little literature that focuses on the mechanisms of influence between the two. Previous research is evident from the above review of the domestic and international literature on Confucian culture and true surplus management.

First, Confucianism, as the most important informal institution in China, has been richly researched, and a large number of scholars have explored its influence on corporate decision-making. The existing literature has shown that Confucian culture can have a significant effect on corporate governance, corporate innovation behaviour, corporate social responsibility and risk-taking ability, and in recent years some scholars have attempted to verify the influence of Confucian culture on corporate surplus management.

Secondly, the existing literature is already rich in studies related to corporate surplus management, but most of the literature targets accrual surplus management and there is a lack of literature from the perspective of real surplus management.

Thirdly, a large number of studies have shown that management engages in true surplus management through the five main instruments of sales control, expense control, production control, asset sales and share buybacks when companies fail to achieve the forecasted economic results. There is currently no academic consensus on the economic impact of this. One view is that true surplus management can lead to deviations in a company's operations, which in turn affect its long-term interests; the second view is that such behaviour occurs incidentally, has little impact on business operations and can convey a good outlook and have a positive effect on institutional investors.

Fourthly, as the cornerstone for constructing the national spirit, culture has a subtle influence on economic behaviour. Confucian culture is a typical informal system of the Chinese nation, and it plays a

non-negligible role in the decision-making of domestic companies. Academics currently lack some attention to traditional culture, and previous studies have mostly explored the impact on true surplus management from the formal system, with little literature quantifying the informal system from a cultural perspective and conducting empirical research on this basis, which leaves enough room for this paper.

III. Theoretical Analysis and Research Hypothesis

(i) Confucian culture and corporate true surplus management

After millennia of development, Confucianism has become the ideological source of traditional Chinese culture. Through research and analysis of the existing literature, this paper argues that Confucian culture can have both a shackling effect and an incentive effect on firms' true surplus management behaviour, and therefore proposes two competing hypotheses.

1. The shackling effect of Confucian culture on corporate true surplus management

Benevolence, righteousness, propriety, wisdom and faith are the 'five constants' of Confucianism, the basic moral code of 'being human' advocated by Confucianism, and have become an important part of Chinese social values. Confucius spoke of benevolence, Mencius of righteousness and Xunzi of propriety. Today, it is generally accepted that the Five Constants of Confucianism are "benevolence, righteousness, propriety, wisdom and trust".

"Ren" is one of the most important core values of Confucianism and is explained in the Analects of Confucius as "Ren is a man who wants to establish himself and to establish others, and who wants to reach others. In the Analects of Confucianism, it is explained as "a man who wants to be established and to attain others, and who wants to attain others". Under the influence of benevolent thinking, management will restrain selfish motives and put the overall interests of the company first, thus reducing the probability of non-compliance and reducing true surplus management behaviour.

"In the Analects of Confucius - Liren, it is said that "A gentleman is a metaphor for righteousness, but a villain is a metaphor for profit". The gentleman is able to sacrifice profit in comparison to moral righteousness. True surplus management is mostly a deviation from morality, and the high moral standards of Confucian culture may inhibit such behaviour by corporate management.

"Ritual" refers to a solid moral identity and positioning of people in different classes with respect to their social status, requiring that words and actions are morally and normatively in line with that status. The Analects of Confucius - Yan Yuan says: "Restrain yourself and return to ritual", advocating control of your true desires, in which case corporate management may abandon true surplus management practices that seriously violate "restrain yourself", leading to a more disciplined production and operation of the company.

"Wisdom" implies the ability to understand right from wrong, right from wrong, right from wrong, true from false, implying that managers are able to make the right corporate decisions and take into account the bigger picture. True surplus management helps to achieve performance targets in the short term, but undermines the long-term value of the business and is not consistent with the ability to distinguish between right and wrong as required by "wisdom".

"Faith" refers to integrity, and is influenced by the Confucian culture that "if a person does not have faith, he does not know what he can do", and the ethics of "utmost sincerity" will influence the rules and norms of behaviour followed by the organisation and its members, and restrain the egoistic mentality of the management. The ethical concept of "sincerity" influences the rules and behaviours of the organisation and its members, and restrains the egoistic mentality of the management. Li Wei et al. (2020) [35] found that the Confucian culture's emphasis on "faith" can have a restraining effect on management's unethical behaviour.

2. The incentive effect of Confucian culture on corporate true surplus management

It is undeniable that Confucian culture also contains the idea of authoritarianism, of which "face culture" is an important part, and is a historical evolution of traditional Confucian ideas of propriety and virtue, which is gradually becoming a culture in Chinese society today.^[36] In China, the need to save face is an important psychological trait that influences individual behaviour. Management has an incentive to engage in truthful surplus management behaviour in order to maintain its reputation, whitewashing financial data and communicating the company's good prospect expectations to the market.

The importance of career prospects is also an important factor influencing the motivation for true surplus management^[37], the external labour market is rife with information asymmetries, and company performance is considered the best indicator of an executive's competence^[38]. Managers, motivated by egoism, are likely to prove their professional worth by improving firm performance through true surplus management. Xie, Deren et al. (2018)^[39] found that managers would achieve performance targets through true surplus management and other means that could be detrimental to the long-term interests of the firm.

In general, Confucianism is a rich philosophical system, but "benevolence, righteousness, propriety, wisdom and trust", the core of Confucianism, has a much higher degree of influence than other ethics. In companies that are deeply influenced by Confucian culture, management may have higher requirements for their own ethics and more stringent enforcement of laws and regulations^[40], thus reducing the frequency of true surplus management behaviour. Based on the above analysis, this paper proposes the following basic hypothesis.

Hypothesis 1: All else being equal, Confucian culture has a significant inhibiting effect on the level of true corporate surplus management.

(ii) The moderating role of internal and external monitoring mechanisms

According to the theoretical basis, the main reason for the occurrence of true surplus management is human, i.e. management, which is subject to internal and external supervision in the decision-making process. (1) Confucian culture advocates the ideas of "righteousness" and "faith", which help regulate the behaviour of corporate management and reduce the level of true surplus management by improving internal supervision mechanisms; (2) Confucian culture values collectivism and "righteousness over profit", which urge management to choose a larger and more effective external supervision system, thus acting as a restraint on management. (2) Confucian culture, with its emphasis on collectivist interests and the value of "righteousness over profit", will encourage management to choose a larger and more effective external monitoring system, thus acting as a restraint on management and reducing the likelihood of true surplus management.

For further research, this paper measures internal oversight mechanisms with internal controls and external oversight mechanisms with external auditors by testing the moderating effects of the potential channels of action described above, with reference to the choice of variables in Holler (2019)^[41] and Song Jianbo et al. (2018)^[42].

1. The reconciliation effect of internal control

Since the enactment of SOX in the US, scholars have gradually begun to focus on the intersection of internal control and true surplus management, and there are currently two different views in the academic community. One believes that true surplus management is the work of corporate management, and its implementation itself requires the support of management and the cooperation of relevant departments, so as long as it does not violate the processes and policies of corporate internal control or involve irregularities, it cannot be bound by internal control. Fan Jinghua et al. (2013)^[43] found through empirical analysis that the inhibitory effect of internal controls on true surplus management was not significant. Another argues that an effective internal control mechanism is an import

ant corporate governance mechanism that can restrain management behaviour and corporate irregularities^[44]. If the internal control system of a company is well developed, the board of directors and supervisors can play a supervisory role and can effectively curb corporate true surplus management behaviour and improve the quality of surplus.

Based on the above discussion, this paper argues that the disincentive effect of Confucian culture on corporate surplus management can be strengthened only when the internal control mechanism of the firm is effective, i.e., when it can create restraints on management's irregularities, and that there is no significant effect when internal controls are inadequate, and proposes a second hypothesis.

Hypothesis 2: When internal controls are effective, they reinforce the inhibiting effect of Confucianism on true surplus management.

2. The moderating effect of external audit

Previous literature shows that external audit, as an independent economic regulatory activity, can authentically identify and curb financial irregularities of enterprises, including true surplus management (Cai Chun et al. 2005; Fan Jinghua et al. 2013; Cao Guohua et al. 2014). On the one hand, under the current premise of open audit information, if an accounting firm does not detect misstatement fraud, etc. in a firm, it will be subject to public accusation and legal punishment, so it will identify audit risks and ensure audit quality as far as possible. On the other hand, true surplus management is highly concealed and can only be identified and controlled by experienced firms with solid expertise; and the higher the quality of the audit, the greater the likelihood of detecting true surplus management. In addition, Confucian culture implies the idea of prioritising collective interests, which will prompt management to choose a reputable and large accounting firm to enhance their own reputation (Hou Shiyong et al., 2020). Therefore, the author argues that external auditing will strengthen the inhibitory effect of Confucian culture on true surplus management and proposes the following hypothesis.

Hypothesis 3: External audit reinforces the inhibiting effect of Confucian culture on true surplus management.

IV. Study Design

(i) Data sources and sample processing

In this paper, we selected the data of A-shares in Shanghai and Shenzhen markets from 2015 to 2019 as the sample, and the data were collected from CSMAR database, Diebold database and manually, and the data were processed and analyzed by using Excel and Stata, and finally we obtained 1,969 companies with a total of 9,845 data values.

The paper screens the primary sample according to the following criteria.

(1) Removing the sample of listed companies such as finance and insurance, and referring to the 2012 Classification Guidelines for Listed Companies for industry classification.

(2) Removal of the sample of ST/ST* companies, where there are abnormalities in the operating conditions of such enterprises.

(3) Relevant data with missing values, outliers and extreme values were excluded.

(4) To prevent the effect of extreme values, a 2.5% reduction in tail has been applied to all continuous variables.

(ii) Definition and description of variables

1. Explanatory variable: Real surplus management

Currently, most scholars use Roychowdhury's algorithm as the basis for calculating REM and use it to

measure the level of true surplus management quality. Therefore, this paper refers to Roychowdhury (2006), Xu Peng (2021) ^[45] and other scholars' methods to measure the true surplus management of listed companies, firstly, the data are estimated by industry and year to obtain the normal cash flow from operating activities, normal production costs and normal discretionary expenses; then the actual values of the company in the current year are differed from the estimated normal values to obtain the abnormal operating activities Cash flow from abnormal operating activities (Y_CFO), abnormal production costs (Y_PROD) and abnormal discretionary expenses (Y_DISEXP).

(1) The cash flow model for operating activities is measured by equation 4.1.

$$\frac{CFO_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} = a_0 + a_1 \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + a_2 \frac{S_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + a_3 \frac{\Delta S_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4.1)$$

where $CFO_{i,t}$ denotes net cash flow from operating activities for the period, and $A_{i,t-1}$ denotes total assets at the end of the previous period, and $S_{i,t}$ is sales revenue for the current period, and $\Delta S_{i,t}$ is the change in sales revenue from the current period to the previous period and the production cost model is measured by equation 2. $S_{i,t}$ is sales revenue for the current period, and $\Delta S_{i,t}$ is the change in sales revenue between the current and prior period, and $\Delta S_{i,t-1}$ is the change in sales revenue between the prior period and the prior period, as follows

(2) The production cost model is measured by equation 4.2.

$$\frac{PROD_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} = a_0 + a_1 \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + a_2 \frac{S_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + a_3 \frac{\Delta S_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + a_4 \frac{\Delta S_{i,t-1}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4.2)$$

where $PROD_{i,t}$ represents the cost of production for the period and is the sum of cost of goods sold and changes in inventories.

(3) The discretionary cost model is measured by equation 4.3.

$$\frac{DISEXP_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} = a_0 + a_1 \frac{1}{A_{i,t-1}} + a_2 \frac{S_{i,t}}{A_{i,t-1}} + \varepsilon_{i,t} \quad (4.3)$$

$DISEXP_{i,t}$ Represents discretionary expenses for the period and is the sum of administrative expenses and selling expenses.

The final true surplus management (REM) is measured by equation 4.4.

$$REM = Y_PROD - Y_CFO - Y_DISEXP \quad (4.4)$$

2. Explanatory variable: degree of Confucian cultural influence

There is no direct measure of Confucianism as an informal institution. Up to now, the existing literature has mostly started from two methods: first, using distance models to measure the influence of informal institutions on listed companies, calculating the distance from the company's registered office to Confucianism representative addresses such as Confucianism centres and Confucius temples, or selecting the number of Confucianism buildings within a certain radius of the registered office, such as Cheng Bo et al. (2016) ^[46] and Li Xin (2020) ^[47] using the use of the location of listed companies within a certain radius the number of official Confucian schools within the late Ming Dynasty as a variable for the degree of influence of Confucian culture. The second is to use a regional model, a common approach is to count the number of Confucian temples or Confucian schools in a given region and use their weighting within that region as a measurement variable.

In this paper, we choose to refer to Du (2015, 2016) ^[48] to measure the influence variable of Confucianism, using information on the distance from the company's registered office to each Confucianism centre, the seven Confucianism centres in China are Qufu in Shandong, Luoyang in Henan, Chengdu in Sichuan, Dongtai in Jiangsu, the eastern region of Zhejiang, Linchuan in Jiangxi and Sanming and Longyan in Fujian province, this paper uses Baidu map to capture the above seven Confucianism centres' This paper uses Baidu Maps to capture the latitude and longitude coordinates of the above seven Confucianism centres, and also collects the latitude and longitude coordinates of the registered offices of all A-share listed

companies, and uses this data to calculate the average distance from the registered office to each Confucianism centre. The details are as follows.

(1) Obtain the latitude and longitude of the sample companies and Confucianism centres, using φ_{lo} , φ_{la} denoting the latitude and longitude of the company's place of incorporation, the ω_{lo} and ω_{la} denote the latitude and longitude of the Confucianism centre, and use the following formula to calculate $\cos\alpha$: The latitude and longitude of

$$\cos\alpha = \sin\varphi_{la} * \sin\omega_{la} + \cos\varphi_{la} * \cos\omega_{la} * \cos(\varphi_{lo} - \omega_{lo})$$

(2) Calculated arc length.

$$\text{rad} = \frac{40075.04}{360^\circ} * \frac{180^\circ}{\pi}$$

(3) Calculate the distance between each company and the seven Confucian centres.

$$\text{DIS}_i = \text{rad} \times \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan\left(\frac{\cos\beta}{1 - \cos^2\beta}\right) \right)$$

(4) Variables to measure the extent of Confucian influence were obtained.

$$\text{Congfu} = \frac{\text{MAX_DIS}_i - \text{AVG_DIS}_i}{\text{MAX_DIS}_i - \text{MIN_DIS}_i}$$

DIS_i denotes the distance between the company and each Confucian Centre ($i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7$), MAX_DIS_i , MIN_DIS_i and AVG_DIS_i denote the maximum, minimum and average of the seven distance values, respectively, and the resulting indicator Congfu is the final measurement variable.

3. Moderating variables

In this paper, internal control and external audit are selected separately as moderating variables.

(1) Internal controls

For the measurement of internal control indicators, this paper refers to the variable selection of Holler (2019) ^[49] and Song Jianbo et al. (2018) ^[50] to measure the internal monitoring mechanism by internal control, and draws on the practice of Du Jianju (2021) ^[51] and other scholars to adopt the "Diebold internal control index/100" to measure the effectiveness of internal control. The higher the internal control evaluation index, the better the effectiveness of internal control.

(2) External Audit

For the measurement of external control indicators, the current literature measures different methods, mainly including whether the firm is a Big Four, the type of audit opinion, and audit fees. In this paper, the purpose of studying external audit is to understand the selection of audit firms by enterprises, and with reference to Shi Hongtao (2019) ^[52], whether the audit is performed by an international Big Four accounting firm (KPMG, Ernst & Young, PricewaterhouseCoopers, Deloitte) is set as a dummy variable (BIG4), taking 1 when audited by the Big Four and 0 otherwise.

4. Control variables

A review of the relevant literature reveals that there are many additional factors affecting the level of true surplus management in this paper, and this paper therefore controls for the following dummy variables.

Company size (SIZE), management shareholding (GGL), executive compensation (TOP3), number of board meetings (DMEET), return on assets (ROA), earnings per share (EPS), operating expense ratio (OER), degree of accrued surplus management (DA), and also control for industry dummy variables (IND) and year dummy variables (YEAR), with each variable's specific The names are shown in Table 4.1.

Table 4.1 Definition and description of variables

Variable type	Variable name	Variable symbols	Definition and description
Explained variables	Corporate true surplus management	REM	REM calculation based on Roychowdhury's algorithm
Explanatory variables	The extent of Confucian cultural influence	Congfu	Confucianism measurement variables based on distance models of business incorporation and seven Confucianism centres
Adjustment variables	Internal controls	IC	Dibble Internal Control Index / 100
	External Audit	BIG4	Dummy variable, take 1 if the auditor is a Big 4, otherwise take 0
Control variables	Company size	SIZE	Natural logarithm of total assets
	Management shareholding	GGL	Number of shares held by directors and supervisors as a percentage of the total number of shares
	Executive Compensation	TOP 3	Number of times the Audit Committee met during the year
	Number of board meetings	DMEET	The number of Board meetings during the year is taken as the natural logarithm
	Return on assets	ROA	Net Profit / Average Total Assets, Average Total Assets = (Total Assets Closing Balance + Total Assets Opening Balance) / 2
	Earnings per share	EPS	Equals net profit/total number of shares
	Operating expense ratio	OER	Equal to (overheads + selling expenses)/main operating income
	Level of accrued surplus management	DA	Referring to Dechow's (1995) modified Jones model, which refers to the absolute value of manipulation of accrued profits, the larger the DA, the greater the scope for surplus management and the lower the quality of accounting information
	Industries	IND	Dummy variables
Annual	YEAR	Dummy variables	

(iii) Model construction

1. Validating Confucian culture and corporate true surplus management

To test the hypotheses of this paper, a multiple regression linear model was constructed. This paper focuses on the role of Confucian culture on firms' true surplus management. To test hypothesis 1, the following panel regression model (1) was constructed.

$$REM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Congfu}_{i,t} + \beta_2 \text{SIZE}_{i,t} + \beta_3 \text{GGL}_{i,t} + \beta_4 \text{TOP3}_{i,t} + \beta_5 \text{ROA}_{i,t} + \beta_6 \text{EPS}_{i,t} + \beta_7 \text{OER}_{i,t} + \beta_8 \text{DA}_{i,t} + \text{YEAR} + \text{IND} \quad (1)$$

In the model, the explanatory variable is the firm's true surplus management (REM), the core explanatory variable is the influence of Confucian culture (Congfu), which indicates the extent to which firms are

influenced by Confucian culture, YEAR is the year dummy variable, IND is the industry dummy variable, i represents the firm, and t represents the year. the coefficient of Congfu reflects the influence of Confucian culture on firms' true surplus management, and if the coefficient is significantly negative, i.e. $\beta_1 < 0$, then hypothesis 1 holds, proving that Confucian culture will have a dampening effect on the level of true corporate surplus management.

2. Validating the reconciliation effect of internal controls

To test the moderating effect of internal controls, model (2) was constructed.

$$REM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Congfu_{i,t} + \beta_2 Congfu_{i,t} * IC_{i,t} + \beta_3 IC_{i,t} + \beta_4 GGL_{i,t} + \beta_5 TOP3_{i,t} + \beta_6 ROA_{i,t} + \beta_7 EPS_{i,t} + \beta_8 OER_{i,t} + \beta_9 DA_{i,t} + YEAR + IND \quad (2)$$

Model (2) additionally adds the moderating variable Internal Control IC and the interaction variable IC*Congfu to model (1). If the interaction term is not significant, then internal control does not play a moderating role, then hypothesis 2 is tested, and the remaining control variables are the same as the hypothesis 1 model.

3. Validating the moderating effect of external audit

To test hypothesis 3 and to test the moderating effect of external audit, model (3) was constructed.

$$REM = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Congfu_{i,t} + \beta_2 Congfu_{i,t} * BIG4_{i,t} + \beta_3 BIG4_{i,t} + \beta_4 GGL_{i,t} + \beta_5 TOP3_{i,t} + \beta_6 ROA_{i,t} + \beta_7 EPS_{i,t} + \beta_8 OER_{i,t} + \beta_9 DA_{i,t} + YEAR + IND \quad (3)$$

Model (3) additionally adds the moderating variable external audit BIG4 and the interaction variable BIG4*Congfu to model (1), which acts as an enhancement to test hypothesis 3 if the coefficient on the interaction term is significant and has the same sign as the core explanatory variable Congfu, and the remaining control variables are the same as in the hypothesis 1 model.

V. Analysis of the empirical results

(i) Descriptive statistics

Table 5.1 reports the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the main test, with a mean value of 2.278 for the explanatory variable REM and a mean value of 0.506 for the explanatory variable Congfu, representing an average Confucian atmosphere strength of around 0.506 for the sample listed companies. The mean value of Internal Control (IC) is 6.46, which is closer to the maximum value of 7.81, and the mean value of BIG4 is only 0.0673, indicating that only 6.73% of the companies listed in the sample employ a Big 4 accounting firm. The rest also show the results of descriptive statistics for the control variables.

Table 5.1 Descriptive statistical analysis

VARIABLES	(1) Number	(2) Average value	(3) Variance	(4) Minimum value	(5) Maximum value
REM	9,845	2.278	0.909	0.336	4.004
Congfu	9,845	0.506	0.0794	0.359	0.652
IC	9,845	6.460	0.835	3.193	7.810
BIG4	9,845	0.0673	0.251	0	1
SIZE	9,845	22.58	1.230	20.49	25.71
GGL	9,845	9.693	15.44	0	53.35
TOP 3	9,845	14.62	0.650	13.36	16.22

DMEET	9,845	2.256	0.392	1.386	3.091
ROA	9,845	0.0375	0.0481	-0.108	0.155
EPS	9,845	0.338	0.452	-0.694	1.746
OER	9,845	0.584	0.375	0.112	1.801
DA	9,845	0.0647	0.0641	0.00220	0.289

(ii) Correlation analysis

Table 5.2 reports the results of the correlation tests for the main variables. The explanatory variable REM is negatively correlated with the explanatory variables, indicating that Confucian culture may have a dampening effect on true surplus management, tentatively testing hypothesis 1.

Table 5.2 Correlation analysis

REM	Congfu	IC	BIG4	SIZE	GGL	TOP 3	DMEET	ROA	EPS	OER	DA
1											
-0.00500	1										
0.054***	-0.049***	1									
-0.017**	-0.077***	0.126***	1								
-0.063***	-0.089***	0.205***	0.356***	1							
0.00800	0.084***	-0.034***	-0.127***	-0.301***	1						
0.065***	-0.039***	0.149***	0.218***	0.439***	-0.116***	1					
0.043**	0	-0.029**	0.00400	0.249**	0.019*	0.147**	1				
0.167***	0.00600	0.361***	0.045***	0.042***	0.078***	0.182***	-0.086***	1			
0.118***	-0.045***	0.400***	0.186***	0.372***	-0.087***	0.345***	-0.00300	0.738***	1		
0.145***	0.0140	0.134***	0.069***	0.055***	-0.092***	0.144***	-0.049***	0.140***	0.185***	1	
0.165**	0.00500	-0.0100	-0.040**	-0.076**	0.039**	-0.043**	0.087**	-0.083**	-0.062**	-0.00400	1

(iii) Overall effect test

In this paper, the short panel data regressions for 2015-2019 were selected and in the model sel

action, firstly the LM test obtained a p-value of 0.0000, indicating a highly significant random effect. Using the Hausman test again, the original hypothesis of mixed regression was not rejected, so all models were regressed using fixed effects. To test whether hypothesis 1 holds, the regression results are given in Table 4.

As shown in Table 5.3, the coefficient of the explanatory variable Congfu is negative at the 5% level of significance, testing hypothesis 1, indicating that Confucian culture has a disincentive effect on corporate true surplus management, that the high ethical standards of Confucian culture constrain the self-interested behaviour of corporate management, and that the more influenced by Confucian culture, the lower the level of corporate true surplus management.

In terms of control variables, there is a significant negative relationship between firm size (SIZE), return on assets (ROA) and operating expense ratio (OER) and true surplus management at the 1% level, indicating that the larger the firm and the higher the ROA and OER, the more likely it is to have true surplus management problems.

Table 5.3 Regression of overall effects

VARIABLES	(1) REM
Congfu	-1.834** (-2.31)
SIZE	0.122*** (3.54)
GGL	0.001 (0.61)
TOP 3	-0.058* (-1.77)
DMEET	0.045 (1.23)
ROA	2.690*** (6.37)
EPS	-0.094* (-1.77)
OER	0.320*** (4.99)
DA	1.771*** (12.96)
R-squared	0.049

(iv) Further group testing

Through the above regressions, the empirical results suggest that Confucian culture in general inhibits firms' true surplus management behaviour. Based on the above observations, the paper further runs separate regressions for the nature of the firm, the age of the firm and the degree of openness to the outside world.

1. Nature of the business

China's capital market is still not well developed and many listed companies are transformed from the shareholding system of state-owned enterprises, and the issue of state-owned enterprises has to

be taken seriously in the study. State-owned enterprises are subject to policy regulation and their decision-making behaviour is to a certain extent political, with the objective not necessarily to maximise shareholders' interests in general terms. Therefore, the management of non-SOEs are relatively more willing to implement true surplus management.

As can be seen from the results in the table, the Confucian culture influence variable is significantly negative at the 1% level in non-state owned enterprises, while it is not significant in state owned enterprises. This implies that the inhibitory effect of Confucian culture on firms' true surplus management is more significant in non-state owned firms.

2. Age of the business

According to the enterprise life cycle theory, the enterprise stage can be divided into four growth stages. As the sample enterprises selected for this paper are all listed and operating normally, they are considered to be enterprises that have passed the start-up stage and will not reach the decline stage, i.e. in the growth or maturity stage. Firms in the growth stage are in urgent need of growth and have a stronger incentive to implement true surplus management, while firms in the maturity stage are highly profitable and have a lower level of true surplus management. To further test whether the age of the firm has an impact on the relationship between Confucianism and true surplus management, this paper chooses to use the annual industry median of age as the dividing criterion and divide it into a growth stage group and a maturity stage group, and test it within the two groups respectively.

The results found that the Confucianism variable was significantly negative at the 5% level in the group of firms whose age was less than the annual industry average, i.e. the growth period group; however, the effect of Confucianism culture on true surplus management was negative but not significant in the maturity period group. This indicates that Confucian culture has a high degree of inhibition of true surplus management in mature stage firms relative to mature stage firms.

3. Degree of openness to the outside world

As China becomes more open to the outside world, the impact of foreign culture will be greater in regions with a higher degree of openness to the outside world; will this have an impact on the inhibitory effect of Confucian culture? In this paper, we refer to Xia Lijun et al. (2007)^[53], where the degree of openness to the outside world is taken as 1 if the company is registered in an open coastal city or special economic zone, and 0 otherwise, and use this as the benchmark for group regression.

As shown in Table 5.4, the core explanatory variables are significantly negative at the 5% level, and the effectiveness of Confucian culture in inhibiting true surplus management is higher in regions with low levels of openness to the outside world.

Table 5.4 Regression analysis of subgroups

Variables	(1) State-owned enterprises REM	(2) Non-state enterprises REM	(3) Maturity REM	(4) Growth period REM	(5) Low level of openness to the outside world REM	(6) High degree of openness to the outside world REM
Congfu	0.440 (1.423)	-3.137*** (0.999)	-0.874 (1.149)	-2.722** (1.117)	-2.094** (0.969)	-2.841 (2.305)
SIZE	0.0775	0.166***	0.0724	0.192***	0.139***	0.0748

	(0.0597)	(0.0441)	(0.0503)	(0.0504)	(0.0424)	(0.0591)
GGL	0.0128	-0.000256	-0.00548	0.00240	0.00510**	-0.00491
	(0.0162)	(0.00196)	(0.00531)	(0.00209)	(0.00225)	(0.00326)
TOP 3	-0.0902	-0.0275	-0.103**	-0.0671	-0.107***	0.00905
	(0.0555)	(0.0417)	(0.0472)	(0.0469)	(0.0399)	(0.0584)
DMEET	0.0914	0.0102	0.00581	0.0640	0.0462	0.0356
	(0.0589)	(0.0463)	(0.0519)	(0.0502)	(0.0436)	(0.0636)
ROA	2.027**	2.684***	1.317**	3.780***	3.019***	1.999***
	(0.811)	(0.520)	(0.614)	(0.601)	(0.520)	(0.721)
EPS	-0.0799	-0.0950	0.0830	-0.248***	-0.154**	0.0268
	(0.0838)	(0.0707)	(0.0707)	(0.0809)	(0.0644)	(0.0933)
OER	0.383***	0.323***	0.269***	0.367***	0.438***	0.0727
	(0.109)	(0.0813)	(0.0861)	(0.101)	(0.0794)	(0.110)
DA	2.292***	1.543***	2.013***	1.626***	1.672***	2.026***
	(0.240)	(0.170)	(0.208)	(0.184)	(0.167)	(0.237)
R-squared	0.047	0.056	0.050	0.056	0.051	0.058

(v) Test for moderating effects

1. Internal controls

A hierarchical regression was used to verify the effect of internal control on Confucian culture and corporate true surplus management. The first step was to do an overall regression, the second step introduced the internal control (IC) independent variable, and the third step decentered the two independent variables and introduced the interaction term between the internal control and Confucian culture variables (IC*Congfu). The regression results are shown in Table 5.5.

Table 5.5 Regression of the moderating effect of internal controls

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)	(3)
	Overall REM	Introducing Internal controls REM	Introducing Interaction items REM
Congfu	-1.834** (0.794)	-1.855** (0.794)	-1.854** (0.794)
IC		0.0195 (0.0129)	0.0193 (0.0130)
IC*Congfu			0.0764 (0.432)
SIZE	0.122*** (0.0343)	0.118*** (0.0344)	0.118*** (0.0344)
GGL	0.00112 (0.00184)	0.00111 (0.00184)	0.00110 (0.00185)
TOP 3	-0.0581* (0.0328)	-0.0571* (0.0328)	-0.0570* (0.0328)
DMEET	0.0445 (0.0360)	0.0446 (0.0360)	0.0447 (0.0360)

	(1)	(2)	(3)
ROA	2.690*** (0.422)	2.620*** (0.425)	2.618*** (0.425)
EPS	-0.0936* (0.0530)	-0.102* (0.0533)	-0.102* (0.0533)
OER	0.320*** (0.0642)	0.316*** (0.0643)	0.316*** (0.0643)
DA	1.771*** (0.137)	1.762*** (0.137)	1.762*** (0.137)
R-squared	0.049	0.050	0.050

The coefficients of the interaction term IC*Congfu in the table were tested and did not pass the significance test and the internal control coefficients were not correlated with the dependent variable, which required further validation according to the steps of the moderating effect analysis. The sample was divided into two groups according to the mean of the internal control variables, still using true surplus management as the dependent variable, and separate regression analyses were conducted to determine whether they were homogeneous moderating variables, and the regression results are shown in Table 5.6.

Table 5.6 Regression of internal control groupings

VARIABLES	(1)	(2)
	Low effectiveness of internal controls REM	High effectiveness of internal controls REM
Continued from Table 5.6		
Congfu	-1.171 (1.286)	-3.821*** (1.238)
SIZE	0.224*** (0.0616)	0.0690 (0.0526)
GGL	0.000768 (0.00306)	0.00102 (0.00288)
TOP 3	-0.138** (0.0590)	-0.0179 (0.0475)
DMEET	0.00472 (0.0631)	0.0369 (0.0526)
ROA	2.222*** (0.752)	3.451*** (0.719)
EPS	-0.194* (0.104)	-0.156** (0.0773)
OER	0.261** (0.118)	0.387*** (0.0955)
DA	0.867*** (0.258)	2.193*** (0.201)
R-squared	0.026	0.063

The results in Table 7 show that for the sample group with above-mean internal control, the coefficient of the Confucianism influence variable is not significant; for the sample group with above-mean internal control, the coefficient of the Confucianism influence variable passes the significance test at the 1% level. We conclude that internal control moderates Confucianism and true corporate surplus

us management when its effectiveness is high and positively at the 1% level; when internal control is weak, the moderating effect of internal control is not significant. And the two groups have different R² values and their Chow test results are also significant, indicating that internal control is a homogeneous moderating variable and hypothesis 2 holds.

2. External audit

A hierarchical regression was used to verify the role of external audit on the influence of Confucian culture and corporate true surplus management. The first step was to do an overall regression, the second step introduced the independent variable of external audit (BIG4), the third step decentered the two independent variables and introduced the interaction term of internal control and Confucian culture variables (BIG4*Congfu), the regression results are shown in Table 5.7.

Table 5.7 Regression of the moderating effect of external audit

	(1)	(2)	(3)
	Overall	Introducing External Audit	Introducing Interaction items
VARIABLES	REM	REM	REM
Continued from Table 5.7			
Congfu	-1.834** (0.794)	-1.834** (0.794)	-1.906** (0.795)
BIG4		0.0859 (0.101)	0.0862 (0.101)
BIG4*Congfu			-2.430** (1.194)
SIZE	0.122*** (0.0343)	0.119*** (0.0344)	0.125*** (0.0346)
GGL	0.00112 (0.00184)	0.00113 (0.00184)	0.00115 (0.00184)
TOP 3	-0.0581* (0.0328)	-0.0592* (0.0328)	-0.0582* (0.0328)
DMEET	0.0445 (0.0360)	0.0451 (0.0361)	0.0458 (0.0360)
ROA	2.690*** (0.422)	2.688*** (0.422)	2.661*** (0.422)
EPS	-0.0936* (0.0530)	-0.0933* (0.0530)	-0.0905* (0.0530)
OER	0.320*** (0.0642)	0.320*** (0.0642)	0.323*** (0.0642)
DA	1.771*** (0.137)	1.771*** (0.137)	1.768*** (0.137)
R-squared	0.049	0.050	0.050

After testing, the coefficient of the interaction term BIG4*Congfu in the table is significantly negative at the 5% level, with the same sign as the core variable Congfu, indicating that external audit plays a reinforcing role between Confucian culture and true corporate surplus management. And th

the coefficients of BIG4 in (2) and (3) are both insignificant, indicating that the relationship between external audit on Confucian culture and true surplus management is a pure moderating effect, testing hypothesis 3.

(vi) Robustness tests

In this paper, the distance model between the place of incorporation of listed companies and seven Confucian centres is used as a variable to measure the degree of influence of Confucian culture. In order to test the robustness of the conclusions drawn from the overall regression, a new Confucian variable is selected in this paper as a way to test the validity of the hypothesis. The imperial examinations used the Confucian classics as official books, and those who came first in the imperial examinations were called scholarship holders. The high number of regional scholarship holders also reflected, to a certain extent, a high degree of influence by Confucian culture. As the imperial examination system of the Qing Dynasty was the most mature in history and the data on scholarship is relatively available, the data on scholarship of the Qing Dynasty was chosen to measure the degree of influence of Confucian culture, specifically expressed as the number of scholarship holders of the Qing Dynasty in the province where the listed company is registered (ZYNUM). The number and region of the scholars is referenced from Qiao Pengcheng et al. (2021)^[54] and collated by hand, and the information on the place of registration of listed enterprises is obtained from CSMAR.

According to the results in Table 5.8, the coefficient of the substitution variable (ZYNUM) in (1) is -0.0196, which is negatively correlated with the dependent variable at the 5% level of significance, providing strong additional support for Hypothesis 1 and indicating robustness of the main regression results. To further verify the robustness of the findings, the paper continues with the moderating effect analysis using the Confucian replacement variable. The interaction terms of the replacement variable and internal control (ZYNUM*IC) in (2) and (3) are not correlated with the dependent and moderating variables, and the results of the subsequent group regressions remain consistent, making the findings of Hypothesis 2 robust. (The interaction term between the proxy variables and external audit (ZYNUM*BIG4) in (4) and (5) remains significantly negative at the 5% level with true surplus management and is not correlated with external audit, indicating that external audit is a purely moderating variable, validating the conclusions of Hypothesis 3.

Table 5.8 Regression results for replacing the Confucianism variable

VARIABLES	(1) REM	(2) REM	(3) REM	(4) REM	(5) REM
ZYNUM	-0.0196** (0.00966)	-0.0199** (0.00966)	-0.0200** (0.00966)	-0.0195** (0.00966)	-0.0190** (0.00966)
IC		0.0196 (0.0129)	0.0155 (0.0138)		
ZYNUM*IC			-0.00132 (0.00152)		
BIG4				0.0845 (0.101)	-0.294 (0.206)
ZYNUM*BIG4					-0.0773** (0.0368)
SIZE	0.119*** (0.0343)	0.116*** (0.0343)	0.117*** (0.0344)	0.116*** (0.0344)	0.118*** (0.0344)
GGL	0.00109	0.00108	0.00106	0.00110	0.00114

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)
	(0.00184)	(0.00184)	(0.00184)	(0.00184)	(0.00184)
TOP 3	-0.0548*	-0.0537	-0.0540*	-0.0559*	-0.0570*
	(0.0328)	(0.0328)	(0.0328)	(0.0328)	(0.0328)
DMEET	0.0426	0.0427	0.0422	0.0431	0.0441
	(0.0361)	(0.0361)	(0.0361)	(0.0361)	(0.0361)
ROA	2.683***	2.613***	2.621***	2.681***	2.674***
	(0.422)	(0.425)	(0.425)	(0.422)	(0.422)
EPS	-0.0910*	-0.0996*	-0.0997*	-0.0906*	-0.0908*
	(0.0530)	(0.0533)	(0.0533)	(0.0530)	(0.0530)
OER	0.314***	0.310***	0.311***	0.314***	0.315***
	(0.0642)	(0.0643)	(0.0643)	(0.0642)	(0.0642)
DA	1.771***	1.761***	1.764***	1.771***	1.768***
Continued from Table 5.8					
	(0.137)	(0.137)	(0.137)	(0.137)	(0.137)
R-squared	0.049	0.050	0.050	0.049	0.050

(vii) Summary of the chapter

This section presents the analysis of the empirical results, which are based on the data, variables and models selected in the previous section and derived through Stata 16.0. The fixed effects model was first identified through LM test and Hausman test, followed by overall regression and moderating effects analysis to test the hypotheses, and finally robustness tests were conducted.

Through empirical evidence, it was found that the degree of influence of Confucian culture would have a significant inhibiting effect on the level of true surplus management, testing hypothesis 1. This effect was more pronounced in private enterprises, growth stage enterprises and regions with low openness to the outside world. Further research found that internal and external monitoring mechanisms would play a moderating role between Confucian culture and true surplus management, with internal control as a homogeneous moderating variable, testing hypothesis 2, and external audit as a pure moderating variable, testing hypothesis 3.

Finally, the findings were tested for robustness by replacing the independent variables originally selected in this paper with the number of Qing dynasty scholars (ZYNUM) in the provinces where the listed companies are registered, and the re-obtained results reconfirmed the above hypotheses, indicating that the empirical results obtained in this paper are robust and valid.

VI. Conclusions and Recommendations of the Study

Using a sample of listed companies from 2015-2019 and the informal system as a starting point, this paper explores the mechanism of the role of Confucian culture on corporate true surplus management. Based on the previous theoretical combinations and the analysis of the empirical results, this paper has the following main conclusions.

(1) There is a significant negative correlation between Confucian culture and the level of true surplus management of a firm, and as the firm becomes more influenced by Confucian culture, its inhibiting effect on true surplus management behaviour becomes more pronounced.

(2) The inhibitory effect of Confucian culture on true corporate surplus management is more pronounced in the sample group of non-state-owned enterprises, long-established enterprises and enterprises located in regions that are less open to the outside world.

(3) Both internal control and external audit play a moderating role between Confucianism and tr

ue surplus management. Internal control is a homogeneous moderating variable, with high quality internal control reinforcing the inhibiting effect of Confucianism on true surplus management, while low quality has no moderating effect. External audit is a purely moderating variable, acting as a positive moderator between the dependent and independent variables.

In summary, Confucianism, as an influential informal institution in Chinese history, has an important impact on corporate true surplus management behaviour, suggesting that the role of informal institutions on corporate decision-making behaviour deserves attention and can complement formal institutions to aid corporate governance. On this basis, this paper makes the following policy recommendations.

(1) When selecting corporate management, consider the extent to which they are influenced by informal systems such as Confucianism. Confucian culture contains high moral values such as benevolence, righteousness, propriety and trust, which can subconsciously regulate the behaviour of management and restrain them from violating the rules.

(2) Make full use of China's excellent traditional culture and attach importance to corporate culture. At present, domestic listed companies attach less importance to corporate culture and lack governance experience. They can draw on the advantages of China's existing rich traditional culture to establish the right values for employees and corporate management and improve corporate governance.

(3) Improve the internal and external supervision mechanism of the enterprise. According to empirical tests, both internal and external supervision mechanisms strengthen the inhibiting effect of Confucian culture on true surplus management when they are effective. Therefore, listed companies should also improve their internal control mechanisms, pay attention to the supervision of external audits, and establish a more reasonable and effective supervision system to restrain the irregularities of corporate management.

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